

Solute-Solvent Interaction in Aqueous PEG Solution

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The hydration and solute-solvent interaction parameters of five polyethylene glycols PEG 200, 300, 400, 600 and 1000, have been reported. The hydration has been unambiguously evaluated using conductance and viscosity methods. A comparison of the important literature cited hydrations of EO group with the results of this study has been made. The viscosity B and C coefficients have been obtained from a quadratic fitting of relative viscosity with mol dm⁻³ concentration of the PEG. The B coefficient has been analysed in the light of molecular size, solvation and water-structure modification. The solute-solute interaction parameter C has been observed to be significant for PEG 600 and 1000. The results are more consistent than that reported by Bahri and Guveli given in reference seventeen.

Polyethylene glycols are very frequently used in industrial and pharmaceutical preparations. They also compose the hydrophilic head groups of many nonionic surfactants and are present in oligocyclic compounds and crowns. Studies of their solution properties are, therefore, important and found in literature¹⁻¹⁴. Recently, we have reported¹⁵ the volumetric behaviour of two polyethylene glycols (PEG 400 and 600) along with other polyhydroxy compounds including several non-ionic surfactants with ethylene oxide residues. In a separate study¹⁶ on the hydration of oil/water microemulsions, several PEGs have been used as calibrating compounds. Contemporary to our reports, Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ presented the results of interaction of PEGs with water and their hydrations from viscometric and volumetric measurements. The results are significantly at variance with our past and recent findings^{15,16}. A critical comparison has revealed that the measured viscosities of Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ were higher than that of ours. This is supported by the earlier reported intrinsic viscosities of PEGs of similar origin¹⁸. Further, the authors have reported that the apparent molal volumes of the PEGs are independent of concentration, which is also an unexpected observation. Our experience in this regard supports significant dependence of apparent molal volumes of the PEGs on concentration. Besides, the literature cited on hydrations of EO group are also mostly inconsistent: results show

variations of the hydration number in the range of less than one to greater than five. A systematic hydration study with graded PEGs adopting more than one method is much wanted.

We have, therefore, elaborately investigated the solution behaviour of a series of polyethylene glycols (PEG 200, 300, 400, 600 and 1000) using viscometric as well as conductometric methods to establish the hydration and volumetric behaviours of the polyethylene glycols on a more certain basis. It will be seen that the hydration and solute-solvent interaction parameters of all the five PEGs used are consistent and significantly different from a number of earlier reports.

Results and Discussion

The commercial PEGs are not homogeneous in respect of molar masses, but are polydisperse. Their numbers correspond to their average molar masses. Informations collected on their physical properties should, therefore, be also average.

The plot of $\log[\eta]$ against $\log M_s$ (where, $[\eta]$ and M_s are the intrinsic viscosity and molar mass respectively) was found to be excellently linear yielding the constants K and a of Mark-Houwink equation ($[\eta] = KM_s^a$) to be 3×10^{-3} and 0.4 from the intercept and the slope respectively. The good

Fig. 1. Apparent molal volume (ϕ_s) vs concentration (m) of the disperse phase plots of (\blacktriangle) EG, (\times) PEG 200, (\oplus) PEG 300, (Δ) PEG 400, (\circ) PEG 600, and (\bullet) PEG 1000 at 303 K. Inset represents partial molal volume (\bar{V}_s^0) vs number of EO groups plot.

linearity supported the usefulness of the average molar masses of the polymers. The values are close to those reported by Bahri and Guveli¹⁷.

Partial molal volume : The apparent molal volumes of the PEGs were evaluated from the density measurements using of relation¹²,

$$\phi_s = \frac{M_s}{d_s} + \left(\frac{d_w - d_s}{d_w d_s m} \right) \times 10^3 \quad (1)$$

where, ϕ_s , M_s , d_w , d_s and m are the apparent molal volume, molar mass of the solute, density of water, density of solution, and molality of the solution, respectively.

The extrapolation of ϕ_s to zero concentration (Fig. 1) gave the partial molal volume \bar{V}_s^0 . There was significant variation of ϕ_s with concentration. Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ reported concentration-independent apparent molal volumes of PEG, which is very unusual. We have also observed appreciable concentration-dependent apparent molal volumes of PEG in the past¹⁵. Therefore, quantitative evaluation of the solvation and interaction parameters of the

PEGs on the basis of apparent molal volume reported by Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ is expected to be in error. The dependence of \bar{V}_s^0 on the number of ethylene oxide groups (EO groups) of the PEGs is presented in the inset of Fig. 1. The \bar{V}_s^0 varies linearly with the number of EO groups. The average \bar{V}_s^0 per EO group is 34 ml mol⁻¹ at 303 K which is 3 units less than that reported by Bahri and Guveli.

Hydration of PEGs : Conductometric and viscometric methods were used for the correct determination of hydration of the PEGs. The modified conductance equation of Bruggeman according to the effective medium theory was shown to be useful in this regard¹⁶,

$$(k_s/k_m)^{2/3} = 1 - f\phi \quad (2)$$

where, k_s and k_m are specific conductances of the solution and the medium respectively, ϕ is the apparent volume fraction of the solute (i.e. volume fraction of non-solvated solute) and f is a correction

factor that accounts for the solvation effect. A plot of $(k_s/k_m)^{2/3}$ and ϕ in dilute solution ($\phi < 0.3$) may yield f , which relates the hydration (g/g) of the solute with the density of the solute (d_s) and that of medium (d_m) as

$$\delta = (f-1) d_m/d_s \quad (3)$$

The δ values derived on the basis of equations (2) and (3) using 0.01 mol dm⁻³ NaCl solution as the conducting medium, are given in Table 1. A supportive evaluation of hydration was done by employing the conductance equation of Moulik¹⁹ in the form,

$$k_s/k_m = 1 - 1.93 \nu_h C \quad (4)$$

where, ν_h is the hydrated specific volume (ml/g) of the solute and C is its concentration (g/ml). The results are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. (k_s/k_m) vs C plots for PEGs from conductance measurements. Symbols are same as in Fig. 1; Δ is the shift in the ordinate scale unit to avoid overlap.

Equation (4) is valid for dilute solutions^{15,19} and the extent of hydration can be obtained by comparing the hydrated specific volume of PEG with its anhydrous specific volume, thus,

$$\delta = (\nu_h - \nu) d_w \quad (5)$$

where, d_w is the density of water. The δ values evaluated by equations (4) and (5) are also presented in Table 1.

From electrical conductivity and water self-dif-

fusion coefficient measurements of aqueous polyethylene oxide solution employing Maxwell²⁰ and Hanoi²¹ equations, Foster *et al.*¹⁴ reported hydration numbers of 3.3 and 2.8 water molecules per EO group respectively. On the basis of Maxwell-Wagner²² and Bruggeman²³ equations, they obtained hydration numbers of 1.8 and 1.6 per EO group respectively. Looyenga²⁴ proposed a general conductivity equation.

TABLE 1 - INTRINSIC VISCOSITY $[\eta]$, CORRECTION FACTOR (f) AND HYDRATION (δ) OF PEGs AT 303 K*

PEG M	$[\eta]$ ml g ⁻¹	f	Eq. 3	Eq. 5	Eq. 8	Average (g/g)
62	1.45	—	—	—	-0.04	-0.04
	± 0.04				± 0.03	
	(2.02)	—	—	—	(-0.07)	
	2.45		0.36	0.40	0.36	0.38
200	± 0.03	1.40	± 0.02	± 0.02	± 0.01	
	(2.73)				(0.24)	
	2.90		0.43	0.45	0.42	0.43
300	± 0.05	1.48	± 0.05	± 0.05	± 0.02	
	(3.48)				(0.54)	
	3.13		0.46	0.47	0.46	0.46
400	± 0.03	1.52	± 0.04	± 0.05	± 0.01	
	(4.30)				(0.87)	
	3.44		0.54	0.55	0.57	0.55
600	± 0.06	1.61	± 0.01	± 0.02	± 0.02	
	(5.10)				(1.20)	
	4.39		1.03	1.12	1.02	1.06
1000	± 0.09	2.16	± 0.03	± 0.05	± 0.03	
	(5.40)				(1.32)	

* Values in parenthesis are from Ref. 17 at 293 K.

In the present notation it is of the form,

$$k_s = [(k_{\text{PEG}} - k_m^{1/3}) \phi + \kappa_\mu^{1/3}]^3 \quad (6)$$

where, k_{PEG} is the conductance of the solute and other terms have their usual significance. Since,

$$k_{\text{PEG}} = 0 \quad (\text{PEG is a non-electrolyte}),$$

$$(k_s/k_m)^{1/3} = (1-f) \phi \quad (7)$$

The need for introduction of a correction factor f has been discussed in connection with equations (2) and (3). Equations (1) and (7) are of similar forms only the exponents on the left-hand-side differ. Processing of the experimental results of the present study according to equation (7) has shown good correlation but the f values obtained have been less than one for all the PEGs used. This is absurd for the minimum value which f may assume is

unity, where the solute does not hydrate at all. It thus appears that equation (7) is not applicable to the aqueous electrolyte solution containing PEG. It leads to negative hydration for all the PEGs which has been found only for the ethylene glycol both by Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ and by us. This has been commented upon at the end of the section.

The δ for the polymers can be also effectively evaluated from the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$, using the relation²⁵,

$$[\eta] = 2.5 (\bar{v}_s^0 + \delta \bar{v}_w^0) \quad (8)$$

where, \bar{v}_s^0 is the partial specific volume of the solute, \bar{v}_w^0 the partial specific volume of water (for dilute solution, $\bar{v}_w^0 = v_w$ (specific volume of water) = d_w^{-1}) and 2.5 is a shape factor for solutes of spherical dimension. The PEGs are considered to assume spherical geometry in solution^{4-6,17}. The evaluation of intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ or $Lt (\eta_{sp}/C)$ is demonstrated in Fig. 3. The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ and

Fig. 3. (η_{sp}/C) vs concentration (C) of the disperse phase plots for EG and PEGs. Symbols are same as in Fig. 1.

the partial molal volume of the PEGs are presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. As expected both the parameters increase with increased molar mass of the PEG.

For the estimation of hydration, the relative viscosity data have been also processed in the light of Eiler's voluminosity equation²⁶,

$$\eta_r = [(1-0.1V\phi)/(1-1.35V\phi)]^2 \quad (9)$$

where, V is the voluminosity defined as the ratio of the hydrated and anhydrous volumes of the solute and ϕ the volume fraction of the anhydrous PEG. The relative viscosity data of all the PEG samples have been found to obey the equation with very good degree of correlation. The results are presented in Table 2. The V values have been found also to increase with the molar mass of the PEG.

TABLE 2 - PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUME (\bar{V}_s^0), VOLUMINOSITY (V) AND MOL/O-CENTER HYDRATION NUMBER (n_h) OF THE PEGs AT 303 K*

PEG Molar mass	(\bar{V}_s^0) ml mol ⁻¹	V^a	n_h^b (mol/O-center)			Average n_h (mol/O-center)
			Eq.3	Eq.5	Eq.8	
62	36.1 ±1.7 (54.4) 12.9	—	—	—	-0.07	-0.07
200	±1.4 (170.0) 210.0	1.08 [0.15]	0.78	0.86	0.76	0.81 (0.52)
300	±3.2 (255.0) 316.0	1.39 [0.78]	0.97	1.01	0.94	0.97 (1.21)
400	±1.6 (339.0) 484.0	1.36 [0.74]	1.06	1.08	1.06	1.07 (2.00)
600	±1.8 (506.0) 733.0	1.63 [1.32]	1.26	1.29	1.34	1.30 (2.81)
1000	±8.10 (841.0)	1.96 [2.04]	2.46	2.67	2.43	2.52 (3.15)

* Values in parenthesis are from Ref. 17 at 298 K. ^a Values in parenthesis are n_h values derived from eq. (9). ^b $n_h = \delta M_p / 18 n_o$, where n_o is the number of oxygen centers in the PEG molecule.

The topic of hydration of ethylene oxide group (EO) in PEG type compounds has been widely studied and in this context the results reported by various workers deserve comparison. The important results in this area are given in Table 3. It is seen that EO group hydrations widely vary from less than one to more than five. It is normally considered that two water molecules can undergo

hydrogen bonding with a ether oxygen. The hydration numbers estimated from conductance measurements differ from that obtained from thermodynamic measurements as well as from spectral studies.

Looking into Table 3 it is certain that systematic study using graded PEG samples have been rarely done. The work of Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ is noteworthy in this respect. The methods adopted by different authors are also different. In an earlier publication the method dependent hydration of polyhydroxy compounds has been reported¹⁵. In the present study independent conductance equations have resulted close hydration values which has been strengthened by the hydration estimated from viscosity measurements. We are in the opinion that the results are reliable. Since PEG of low molar masses have been used, the hydration numbers (m_h) have been expressed per oxygen centre rather than per EO group since the terminal hydroxyl groups are also potential water-binding centres. The trends shown by Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ and by us are the same, only the magnitudes differ. The hydration numbers per oxygen center increase with the molar mass. It is not unusual that the polymers of higher molar masses assume folded (or compact) configuration and may trap more water in the process as the chain-length increases. This gets support from the observation of considerable hydration of polyethylene oxide chains of Tweens in the form of micelles than PEG of comparable chain-length by way of trapping the solvent over and above normal hydration¹⁵.

The m_h values derived from δ of equations (3, 5 and 8) and V of equation (9) are presented in Table 2 along with those of Bahri and Guveli¹⁷. The results based on equations (3, 5 and 8) nicely agree. Equation (5) probably has minorly over-estimated m_h whereas equation (9) has underestimated it. We, therefore, propose that the closely comparable conductometric and viscometric hydration results of the present study are reliable and the average of the three sets of results (given in column 7 of Table 2) can be taken as the hydration extents of the PEG samples. The values are quite different from Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ (values in parenthesis in column 7). Although the authors worked at a temperature 5° lower than the present work, the realised

difference in hydration is greater than that, is due to temperature difference. On the basis of the small temperature dependent hydration of polyhydroxy compounds²⁷, the calculated extent of hydration of PEG 400, 600 and 1000 are not close to those of Bahri and Guveli¹⁷. The lower PEGs hardly show differences in m_h at the two temperatures. Therefore, temperature as a source of the discrepancy is ruled out.

TABLE 3 - COMPARISON OF HYDRATION OF ETHYLENE OXIDE GROUPS EXPRESSED PER MOLE OF OXYGEN CENTER FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

System	Molar Mass	Method	m_h (mol/O-center)
Poly(ethylenoxide) ^a	8000	DSC	1.00
Poly(ethylene glycol) ^b	420, 1000, 4000, 6000	DSC	2.70
Poly(propylene glycol) ^b	425	DSC	1.50
Poly(oxyethylene) ^c	1550	DSC	2.00
Cyclic oligo (oxyethylene) ^d	176	Ultrasonic	1.96
	220	Velocity and compressibility	1.91
	264		1.87
Poly(ethylene oxide) and Poly(vinyl alcohol) ^e	3400 - 600,000	Dielectric relaxation	more than 5.00
α -Methyl- ω -methoxyoligo- (oxyethylene) ^f	90-222	Hypersonic velocities	1.80
α -Methyl- ω -hydroxyoligo- (oxyethylene) ^f	120-164		
Poly(ethylene oxide) ^g	200-14000	Conductance and self-diffusion	1.6-3.3
Poly(ethylene oxide) ^h	2×10^5 and 5×10^6	Conductance	1.00
Poly(ethylene glycol) ⁱ	400, 600	Conductance	2.0
		Ultrasonic	1.3-3.4
		Intra-red	1.5-1.9
Poly(ethylene oxide) ^j	-	Theoretical	2.00

^aRef 8 ^bRef 12 ^cRef 13 ^dRef 9 ^eRef 10 ^fRef 11 ^gRef 14
^hRef 35 ⁱRef 15 ^jRef 7

It is seen that the hydration numbers (number of water molecules associated per oxygen center) vary with the chain-length of the PEG. It is less than one for lower molar mass samples and greater than one for higher molar mass species; for PEG 1000 it is 2.5. It is, therefore, not at all surprising that higher values greater than five exist in literature. But the results are not always consistent in this respect.

In Table 1, δ , $[\eta]$ and \bar{V}_s^0 values for ethylene glycol (EG) are also presented. They make the listing complete. Information derived are not all

significant. A negative hydration has been realised both by us as well as by Bahri and Guveli¹⁷. Physical properties of polymers may not be exhibited by the monomers nor are the relations used necessarily valid for them.

PEG-water interaction : The relative viscosity of a neutral solute may be expressed by a polynomial^{28,29},

$$\eta_r = 1 + BM + CM^2 + \dots \quad (10)$$

where, *B*, *C*, etc. are appropriate coefficients and *M* is the concentration (mol dm⁻³) of the solute. For dilute solution, the third term in the right-hand-side can be neglected and equation (10) reduces to the well known Jones-Dole equation for non-electrolytes³⁰. The *B* coefficient has been shown to be a good measure of structure modification of the solvent by the solute. Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ evaluated *B* and *C* by a polynomial fit of η_r with concentration. Following a similar procedure the *B* and *C* coefficients were found out from the present η_r data and are presented in Table 2. The results of Bahri and Guveli¹⁷ are presented in parentheses. Their *B* values were all higher and *C* values were lower (except PEG 200, 300 and 400) than the present values.

For dilute solutions or dispersions of spherical entities, the relative viscosity follows the Einstein's equation³¹,

$$\eta_r = 1 + 2.5 V_h M \quad (11)$$

where, $V_h M = \phi$, the volume fraction of the solute, V_h being its hydrodynamic molar volume and *M* is the concentration (mol dm⁻³). From equations (10 and 11),

$$B = 2.5 V_h \quad (12)$$

The following discussion is based on certain assumptions and reasonings which are difficult to verify experimentally. The rationale presented, however, accounts for the kinds of interaction the solute can undergo with the solvent and with itself. The assumptions herein considered are commonly used in the study of solution chemistry.

In dilute solutions, the solute-solvent interaction is independent of solute concentration. If the solute weakly interacts with the solvent then, $V_h = \bar{V}_s^0$ and $B_{size} = 2.5 \bar{V}_s^0$ ^{32,34}, where B_{size} is the intrinsic volume of one mole of the solute. Any deviation from this expectation is attributed to the solute-solvent interaction leading to solvent structure modification and solvation. The B_{exp} values are compared with B_{size} ($= 2.5 \bar{V}_s^0$) in Table 4. It is seen that the B_{size} values are lower than B_{exp} and the degree of lowering increases with increasing molar mass of PEG. The lower magnitudes of the B_{size} suggest that the volumetrically estimated $\bar{V}_s^0 < V_h$ due to solvation and solvent structure modification. The change in the volume of the solution per mole addition of a solute under the condition of no solute-solute interaction (in very dilute solution) is called the partial molal volume of the solute. The measured partial molal volume can, therefore, account for the contraction and expansion caused by the interaction of the solute with the solvent. The partial molal volume obviously does not represent the solvated hydrodynamic molar volume of equation (11). The B_{exp} can be split into the contributing terms as

$$B_{exp} = B_{size} + B_{solv} \quad (13)$$

The B_{size} accounts for the non-solvated contribution and its absolute estimate is difficult. It is apparently

TABLE 4—DECIPHERED SOLUTE-SOLVENT INTERACTION PARAMETERS IN AQUEOUS PEG SOLUTION AT 303 K*

PEG Molar mass	B_{exp} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	B_{size} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	B_{solv} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	B_{struc} dm ³ mol ⁻¹
200	0.45±0.005	0.30±0.004(0.48)	0.18±0.004(0.20)	-0.034(-0.03)
300	0.86±0.015	0.53±0.008(0.71)	0.32±0.002(0.38)	0.010(-0.06)
400	1.27±0.013	0.79±0.004(0.95)	0.46±0.009(0.79)	0.016(-0.10)
600	2.13±0.033	1.21±0.005(1.42)	0.86±0.029(1.83)	0.062(-0.15)
1000	5.03±0.093	1.83±0.020(2.36)	2.56±0.073(4.76)	0.640(-1.26)

* Values in parenthesis are from Ref 17 at 298 K.

equivalent to $2.5 \bar{V}_s^0$ because \bar{V}_s^0 includes solvent structure alteration effect which is difficult to separate from \bar{V}_s^0 to get the true size effect. The B_{solv} is, however, equal to $(0.0025 M_s \delta / d_w)$ assuming the density of the solvated water to be identical with that of the bulk water (for strong hydration, e.g. primary ionic hydration, the assumption may be tenable). The difference between B_{exp} and the sum of the B_{size} (from \bar{V}_s^0) and B_{solv} (calculated in the above manner) should be attributed to the solvent structural contribution to the B -coefficient (B_{struc}). The results are shown in Table 4. Except for a small negative value for PEG 200 (difficult to rationalise), the B_{struc} is positive and increases slowly with molar mass becoming largely positive for PEG 1000. This indicates contraction in the solvent environment by the presence of the solute which is significant for the largest PEG used. A comparison of B_{size} , B_{exp} and B_{solv} (Fig. 4) reveals

Fig. 4. δ - molar mass of PEG and B_{coeff} - molar mass of PEG profiles in sections A and B respectively.

that while B_{exp} and B_{solv} increase in curvilinear fashion, B_{size} varies in a linear way. This is a reflection of the linear variation of \bar{V}_s^0 with the

number of EO groups presented in the inset of Fig. 1. The large PEG molecules have appreciable contraction effect on the solvent, which lowers the \bar{V}_s^0 with a concomitant increasing B_{struc} contribution. In Fig. 5, the B_{struc} contribution calculated from

Fig. 5. B_{struc} vs molar mass of PEG plots of our work and that of Bahri and Guveli (Ref. 10). Inset represents correlation between C -coefficient and average radius of gyration (R_G).

Bahri and Guveli's data has been compared with the present values. A completely reverse trend has been observed. Their results are all negative, sharply decreasing above PEG 600. Negative B_{struc} coefficients imply expansion in solvent environment by the addition of the solute. This is quite unexpected; hydrated (solvated) solutes typically produce contraction. This unusual result is perhaps due to the incorrect \bar{V}_s^0 used by the authors which were apparent values and higher than the true \bar{V}_s^0 that eventually overestimated B_{size} making the B_{struc} negative.

A comparison of δ as a function of the molar mass presented in Fig. 4 reveals distinct features. Upto PEG 300 the hydration results are comparable. Thereafter, the trends are different, the δ values disagree more than the difference of 5° temperature can account for. It is again the result of inaccurate

TABLE 5 – PARAMETERS OF EQUATION (10) AND THE AVERAGE RADIUS OF GYRATION (R_G) OF PEGs AT 303 K*

PEG	\bar{R}_G Å	Intercept	Correlation (Standard error)	B_{exp} $dm^3 mol^{-1}$	C $(dm^3 mol^{-1})^2$
200	4.27(4.31)	1.001	0.99(0.0027)	$0.45 \pm 0.005(0.63)$	$0.33 \pm 0.033(0.36)$
300	5.17(5.35)	0.995	0.999(0.0017)	$0.86 \pm 0.015(1.02)$	$0.91 \pm 0.103(1.13)$
400	5.83(6.32)	1.002	0.999(0.0016)	$1.27 \pm 0.013(1.64)$	$1.43 \pm 0.013(1.91)$
600	6.89(7.66)	1.002	0.998(0.0035)	$2.13 \pm 0.033(3.10)$	$4.31 \pm 0.418(3.30)$
1000	8.86(9.25)	0.986	0.998(0.0031)	$5.03 \pm 0.093(6.86)$	$13.79 \pm 1.611(7.32)$

*Values in parenthesis (except column 4) are from Ref. 17 at 298 K.

partial specific volume (\bar{v}) used in equation (6) to evaluate δ .

The C -coefficient is reflection of the solute-solute interaction. The C value increases rapidly with the size of the PEG (Table 5). Larger molecules should have higher excluded volumes to show larger non-compatible interaction. The C values are plotted against the average radius of gyration³⁰, $R_G^{-3} = 3 M_s [\eta]/10 \pi N$ in the inset of Fig. 5, where, N is the Avogadro number. The results of Bahri and Guveli increase less rapidly than the present work. The lower C values obtained by the authors for higher PEGs at a lower temperature indicate less solute-solute interaction which is contrary to expectation.

The interrelation among δ , B and C is illustrated in Fig. 6. The base line XZ virtually falls on the diagonal of the base parallelogram on the B - C plane. Therefore, with increasing molar mass of PEG, there is a proportional increase in both B and C , which tends to give deviation at the higher molar mass. A rapid rise in hydration is shown by PEG of lower molar masses (PEG 200, 300); the trend ends at PEG 400 and thereafter, the rise is steady and linear. Small molecules undergo greater interaction with the solvent which is reduced for large molecules due to increased solute-solute interaction.

Experimental

The polyethylene glycols PEG 200, 300 and 1000 (B.D.H.), PEG 400 and 600 (synthesis grade, E. Merck), and ethylene glycol (synthesis grade, E. Merck) were used as before¹⁶. NaCl (A.R., B.D.H.) was used for the preparation of a 0.01 mol dm^{-3} standard electrolyte solution¹⁶. Double-distilled con-

Fig. 6. Three-dimensional profile of the interrelation among hydration (δ), B_{exp} and C -coefficient. Symbols are same as in Fig. 1.

ductivity water of specific conductance $2-3 \mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 303 K was used throughout the experiments.

All measurements were taken at 303 K in a temperature controlled water-bath ($\pm 0.005^\circ$). Conductance measurements were taken with a Jenway (U.K.) conductivity meter at 1 kHz in a cell of cell constant 1.11 cm^{-1} . In actual experiment, the solutions of known concentrations of PEGs in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} NaCl were titrated with the same aqueous electrolyte solution and the conductance at each addition was measured after allowing sufficient time to attain temperature equilibrium.

Viscosities and densities were measured following the procedures described earlier^{16,36}

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